

Ku-Band Dual-Mode filter designed in Microstrip Gap Waveguide Technology

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Abstract—A new version of a dual-mode filter based on microstrip gap waveguide technology is proposed in this paper. The analyzed filter consists of a square ring with a perturbation that produces the coupling of two degenerate modes. In this new configuration, the effect that some of the main parameters have on the filter's bandpass response is studied. This work shows by means of some examples the possibility of designing filters of reduced size in inverted microstrip gap waveguide technology. Two filters have been implemented in the Ku band with a 3 dB fractional bandwidth of 9.3% and 8.6%. The minimum simulated insertion losses for the filters have been 0.4 dB and 0.5 dB respectively. This novel proposal presents an inherent packaging capability and also allows the implementation of bandpass filters with very low losses and increased selectivity.

Index Terms—Dual-mode filter, Gap Waveguide Technology, ring resonator, inverted microstrip.

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of radio technologies is continuously extending both in applications and in frequency spectrum use. In this context, the Gap Waveguide Technology (GWG) [1] allows the design of high-efficiency planar antennas and also many of the necessary elements for signal processing, such as filters [2] [3]. Different types of filters have been proposed in this technology, some closer to their waveguide versions but also others in microstrip technology. The latter have made it possible to cover higher frequency bands in which the conventional microstrip increases its losses. One of the benefits pursued by new designs in passband filters is the circuit packaging, in this sense GWG technology is a competitor of others such as substrate integrated waveguide (SIW) and the technique based on low-temperature cofired ceramic (LTCC) manufacturing [4][5].

In this context, the present work proposes a simple adaptation of a well known filter, based on the dual-mode concept with ring resonator and a printed perturbation. Of course, this element offers the possibility of miniaturizing the filter and a high frequency selectivity that allows designing a band-pass filter with interesting performance. The new inverted microstrip GWG version offers some advantages, the most important are: low losses, improved selectivity and the possibility of being integrated into one of the beam-forming layers above radiating elements in array antennas. It should also be noted that this technology allows the device to be packaged, incorporating the integration into the system

and controlling its impact on the rest of the components in the design procedure. The microstrip filter configuration is sufficiently known, it has been analyzed in detail in [6] [7] [8]. These filters use a resonator that allows to produce orthogonal modes, and by means of a perturbation to excite degenerate modes producing the coupling between filter ports [6]. If there is no perturbation, the symmetry of the resonator only allows orthogonal modes and only one of them would be excited in the input port.

Fig.1. Top view of the printed square ring element with the microstrip line (top). Cross-sectional of the gap waveguide structure with the PMC surface, the substrate and the inverted microstrip elements (down).

Fig.1 shows the structure of the bandpass filter proposed in this work. The filter consists of a square ring resonator ($a=b$) and the perturbation is a small square stub (d) at one of the corners of the resonator. The resonator is fed by a pair of orthogonal inverted microstrip feed lines. The two lines connect to the centre of an approximately quarter wavelength stub with two open ends. The coupling of energy to the resonator occurs through a small gap between the stub and the resonator. Fig. 1 shows us the most important geometric parameters to adjust the filter. These parameters affect the response of the filter while others remain constant in the different simulations. The length of the manuscript does not

allow to delve into some details that will be discussed at the congress. All the simulations have been carried out using the CST Microwave Studio software, using its synthesis tools it has been possible to optimize some of the dimensions.

II. DUAL-MODE SQUARE RING FILTER DESIGN IN INVERTED MICROSTRIP

The operation of GWG technology is based on the use of parallel plate structures in which one of the plates has a periodic artificial surface that functions as a Perfect Magnetic Conductor (PMC). Keeping the distance between the Perfect Electric Conductor (PEC) and the PMC less than $\lambda/4$ avoids propagation of electromagnetic waves [1] [2]. The layers that configure the inverted microstrip GWG technology can be seen in Fig. 2; the lower layer formed by the bed of nails, the substrate layer with the printed filter and its feeding lines is located above and finally the metal cover that closes the parallel plate guide.

Fig.2. Layered description of the 3D model used to study the dual-mode filter.

Because the electric field travels in the gap between the microstrip line (inverted configuration) and the upper part of the guide in this technology, the propagation of the signal occurs in air. This is the main advantage of this technology that avoids the propagation of the field in the substrate and therefore drastically reduces losses. We consider in this section the main steps to design the dual-mode filter.

A. PMC surface description

This GWG version of the dual-mode filter is composed of a printed circuit board without ground plane and supported by a bed of nails, as PMC surface, as Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 show. Fig. 3 shows the geometry of the periodic cell, for the textured PMC surface, and the corresponding Brillouin diagram characterizing the stopband for the GWG in our filter. Key parameters for the stopband are the square geometry of the pin and its dimensions (2mmx2mm), the pin height of 7mm and the periodicity of the structure (5mm). The bed of nails produces a bandgap ranging from 7.4 GHz to 15 GHz which covers the operating Ku bandwidth in our design. In all of the work we have used as dielectric material Rogers 4003, with $\epsilon=3.38$ and $\tan\delta=0.0027$. Also we have kept constant, at value $h=1$ mm, the air gap between the

substrate and the upper plate. The width of the microstrip line is 4.5 mm to achieve 50Ω , considering air propagation for the filed.

Fig.3. Metallic pin model and the numerical dispersion diagram for the surface [9]

B. Dual-mode filter characteristics

Our filters must operate in the Ku-band, which in Europe has a frequency operating range between 10.7-12.75 GHz. Considering that the size of the ring (a-b in Fig. 1) must be approximately $\lambda/4$ and setting a frequency close to 12GHz, the dimensions for the resonator at these frequencies are close to 6 mm [6]. We are going to focus on the design of two filters, one will cover the lower Ku band and the other the upper part of the Ku band. Of course one of the parameters that most affect the coupling of energy in the ring is the gap between the stub and the resonator [7]. This type of filter requires a small gap to avoid high insertion losses, which in practice limits the ability of the device to deliver microwave power. If the gap is small, its effect on the displacement of the resonant frequency is also observed and must be evaluated in the simulations. In our case, a gap has been chosen close to 0.3 mm, which allows adequate tolerances with conventional manufacturing processes but at the same time a good behavior in the coupling.

Fig.4. Simulated S-parameters for the filter for different perturbed stub ($a=5.4$ mm, $w=0.45$ mm, $g=0.3$ mm, $h=1$ mm).

The stub (perturbation) excites the dual-mode operation for the bandpass filter. It is a key element, affecting insertion loss, return loss, and filter bandwidth [6] [7]. In Fig. 4 the

filter response for two sizes of the perturbed stub is shown. We need a minimum size for the stub in the ring to obtain an adequate elliptic function operation. In our case, the values of the stub (d) between 1.1-1.3 mm increase resonance frequency splitting for the modes to obtain an improved bandwidth.

Fig.5 S11 parameter for filters with dimensions ($g=0.3$ mm and $h=1$ mm): dim 1 ($a=6.1$ mm, $w=0.45$ mm $d=1.25$ mm), dim 2 ($a=6.2$ mm, $w=0.45$ mm $d=1.25$ mm), dim 3 ($a=6.2$ mm, $w=0.4$ mm $d=1.3$ mm)

It can be seen from Fig. 5 how it is possible to adjust the response of the filter in the appropriate band by varying the dimensions of the ring, both its side (a) and the width of the loop (w), while the stub performs the splitting in the resonances and fix the band.

C. Feeding lines with stub

An impedance transformer of length (sl) and width (sx) has been included in the feeding lines to control the matching at filter ports (see figures Fig.1 and Fig.2). This configuration aims to minimize return losses in the band maintaining a small coupling gap to achieve low insertion losses. Decreasing the length of the stub that acts as a transformer (initially it has a $\lambda/4$ length) allows to improve port impedance matching as shown in Fig. 6. With feeding line 3 (Fig. 6) a S11 parameter level below -20 dB is obtained in the upper part of the Ku band that includes the frequencies between 12.5 GHz and 12.9 GHz.

Fig.6. Simulated S11-parameter for different feeding lines with impedance transformer ($a=5.4$ mm, $w=0.4$ mm): feed 1 ($sx=1.1$ mm, $sl=5.2$ mm), feed 2 ($sx=1.3$ mm, $sl=5.3$ mm, feed 3 ($sx=1.2$ mm, $sl=4.6$ mm)

III. NUMERICAL RESULTS AND FILTER PERFORMANCE

The results obtained for the dual-mode filter analyzed are shown in this section. The dimensions of the filter have been adjusted to focus its operation on the upper and lower part of the Ku band. Fig. 7 shows the final passband response of the filter covering the lower part of the band. The simulated

center frequency is at 11.06 GHz, the 3-dB fractional bandwidth is 9.3% from 10.55 to 11.58 GHz. Also we observe in the Fig. 7 two transmission zeros at 9.34 GHz and 12.34 GHz respectively. The S11 is below -10dB between frequencies 10.76 GHz and 11.41 GHz. Finally in the Fig. 7 we can see that the out of band rejection level for the filter is below -24 dB in the GWG stopband produced by the PMC surface.

Fig.7. Simulated S-parameters for the filter (lower Ku-band) with main dimensions ($a=6.2$ mm, $d=1.2$ mm, $w=0.4$ mm, $sl=5.3$ mm).

A. Filter operation and E-field distributions

In this section the operation of the new version of the filter in microstrip GWG technology is described by means of the E-field distribution (Fig 8 and Fig. 9) for the dual-mode filter operating in lower Ku-band (with dimensions presented in Fig. 7). Finally, some of its features for optimized designs, at lower and upper Ku bands, will be discussed.

Fig.8. Calculated Max Ez-field component for the proposed filter at two frequencies out of the operation band: a) at $f=7$ GHz and b) at $f=10$ GHz.

It can be seen in Fig. 7 how the GWG structure begins to function correctly from an approximate frequency of 8.5 GHz. That is, up to that frequency the artificial surface formed by pins does not perform its function as PMC and therefore does not prevent the propagation of electromagnetic waves. In the simulation shown in Fig. 8.a) it is clearly appreciated how the field is not confined to the propagation between the inverted microstrip line and the upper cover of the parallel plate waveguide. Consequently at 7 GHz other unwanted EM solutions such as spurious modes and surface waves are excited in the waveguide. On the other hand, in Fig. 8.b) we can see how at a frequency of 10 GHz the pins array work as a PMC surface and prevent the propagation of electromagnetic waves in the volume that is not delimited by the microstrip line. On the other hand, at this frequency, the perturbation of the ring resonator does not produce the degeneration of the orthogonal modes necessary for electromagnetic coupling between ports. Therefore, the filter does not have a passband at this frequency. As a consequence the energy of the input port is only capable of exciting one of the modes and the signal does not reach the output port as clearly shown in Fig. 8.b)

Fig.9. Calculated Max Ez-field component for the proposed filter at a frequency of $f=11.1$ GHz in the operation band.

Finally, Fig. 9 shows us the simulation of the E-field distribution at central frequency for the passband filter. It is observed how the electromagnetic energy is guided by the microstrip line without exciting modes in the parallel plate waveguide. Clearly the field distribution in this case shows the coupling of energy, produced by the perturbed stub, between the degenerate modes of the resonator. Consequently the signal is transmitted, in the lower Ku-band, with high efficiency between the ports in the proposed filter.

B. Numerical results and filter performance

The simulations of the transmission parameter of the filters for the lower and upper Ku bands have been represented in Fig. 10 and Fig. 11 respectively. The plots include the initial simulations carried out (without considering the losses in the metals) and the simulations considering all the losses in the materials; including the

substrate, the copper for the microstrip elements and the aluminum for the pin structure and the metallic covers of the waveguide. The roughness of the metal parts has not been taken into account at the moment.

Fig.10. Simulated S_{21} parameter for the filter operating at lower Ku band: red line without considering losses and blue line with losses.

The simulated minimum insertion losses for lower and upper Ku-band filters are 0.4 dBs and 0.45 dBs respectively. These levels confirm the interest of the proposal to design this novel version of dual-mode filters in the microstrip GWG technology. Although it is reasonable to expect that in future measurements we can verify that these insertion losses could be greater. However, in other previous studies, insertion losses levels between 0.7-1 dB have been measured in the same operating band. We hope to be able to show the measurements on the prototypes analyzed at the conference.

Fig.11. Simulated S_{21} parameter for the filter operating at upper Ku band: red line without considering losses and blue line with losses.

At present, the manufacture of the printed elements of the filter is being carried out to integrate the device. The periodic surface of pins has already been manufactured as shown in Fig. 12.

Fig. 12. Fabricated PMC surface consisting in a Bed of nails

IV. CONCLUSION

This work has shown the design of a new version of a GWG technology microstrip dual-mode filter implemented by means of a square ring resonator. The design steps and dimensions have been specified to achieve two filters that allow band-pass operation at lower and upper frequencies in Ku-band. The designed filters are centered at frequencies of 11.06 GHz and 12.52 GHz, we have verified that the 3-dB fractional bandwidth are 9.3% and 8.6% respectively. Through simulations it has been possible to quantify that these filters can offer sufficient operating bandwidths, enough rejection out of band level and with minimum insertion losses between 0.4 and 0.5 dB. Therefore, this new GWG version of the compact dual-mode ring filter can provide packaged solutions, with low losses and high selectivity. The filter could be integrated into feeding layers in planar antenna arrays.

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